

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 5, No. 6; June 28, 1999

Dear Readers:

With a short delay here is the June issue of J.UCS. Please note that J.UCS has now an entirely new layout (see <http://www.iicm.edu/jucs>), and we will still further improve it over the next month or so. This will cause some minor delays in the publication of the next 2 issues: sorry for this. However, both the submission and annotation process will be made much more transparent and easy this way.

Also, at the Symposium on Developments in Language Theory hosted in Aachen (that also served as a platform for the celebration of Professor Salomaa's 65th birthday, Professor Salomaa being one of the main initiators of J.UCS), three noteworthy events happened: first, Professor Salomaa was informed that the Graz University of Technology has awarded him an honorary doctorate (this is Professor Salomaa's seventh such doctorate!) and that the celebration will take place Nov. 18, 1999 in Graz, Austria. (All those who want to have more information on this please contact me at hmaurer@iicm.edu); second, the book "Jewels are Forever" edited by J.Karhumäki, H.Maurer, G.Paun and G.Rozenberg; Springer Pub.Co. Berlin (1999), ISBN 3-540-65984-6 edited in honor of Professor Salomaa was presented; and third, in a meeting between the editors-in-chief of J.UCS (Calude, Maurer, Salomaa) and Springer representatives (in particular Dr. H. Woessner) new measures to further increase the marketing success of J.UCS were decided upon: as soon as all details are fixed I will inform you immediately.

For now, happy reading, and all the best,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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